

Onto-DESIDE: Ontology-based Decentralized Sharing of Industry Data in the European Circular Economy

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Abstract

The Onto-DESIDE project is a Horizon Europe action, targeting the challenge of accelerating the digital- and green transitions by creating support for information flows in the Circular Economy. The main goal of the project is to develop a technology platform with associated method support for allowing secure decentralized data sharing about materials and products at a global scale by developing (1) a shared vocabulary, i.e. an ontology network, (2) an open circularity platform, based on the Solid family of emerging standards, and (3) methods to analyse and assess new circular value chain configurations (4) validated by 3 industrial use cases. Project duration: June 2022 – November 2025.

Keywords

Circular Economy, Data sharing, Solid, Ontology

1. Project information

The Onto-DESIDE project is a Research and Innovation Action (RIA) under the Horizon Europe programme, Cluster 4 Digital, Industry and Space, from the European Health and Digital Executive Agency. The main goal of the project is to develop a technology for allowing secure decentralized data sharing about materials and products at a global scale by developing a shared vocabulary, an open circularity platform and methods to analyse and assess new circular value chain configurations validated by 3 industrial use cases. Project duration: June 2022 – May 2025.

- Project short name/acronym: Onto-DESIDE
- Project full name: Ontology-based Decentralized Sharing of Industry Data in the European Circular Economy
- Project website link: <https://ontodeside.eu/>
- Start date: 01/06/2022
- End date: 30/11/2025 (extended from 31/05/2025)
- Project status: Ending project
- Funding agency: European Commission
- Funding programme: Horizon Europe
- Call identifier: HORIZON-CL4-2021-RESILIENCE-01
- Project partners: Linköping University (coordinator), University of Hamburg, INTERUNIVERSITAIR MICRO-ELECTRONICA CENTRUM (IMEC), Prague University of Economics and Business, Concular, +Impakt, Circularise, Circular.fashion, Lindner, Ragn-Sells, Texon, Rare Earths Industry Association.
- Project logo: [link](#)

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2. Project summary

The project aims to support the acceleration of the digital and green transitions, through increased circularity of the economy, specifically targeting technologies for enabling the information flows necessary to facilitate circularity. The main goal of the project is to develop and apply an ontology network for data documentation targeting the cross-industry domain of circular economy based on established technologies and standards, and to support the use of the documented data by means of a data sharing platform and methods to set up viable and sustainable value networks. The project includes three industry use cases, i.e. from the textile, electronics and construction industries respectively. The use case support needs analyses, and requirements elicitation, but also provide a test bed for assessing the solutions proposed by the project. Additionally the project both learns from and contributes to ongoing standardisation in the CE field, and produces training material for supporting the use of the technologies beyond the project. In Figure 1 the overall idea of the project is illustrated.

The project has applied an iterative and incremental research methodology, performing three research iterations, each with an evaluation phase for testing the proposed solutions in the use case settings. Currently the project is completing the third iteration, entering the final evaluation phase. In parallel the focus is on future exploitation, providing training material based on project solutions, and disseminating project results. Due to a delay in onboarding a new project partner in the second project iteration, the project timeline will be extended from June 2025 to November.

Figure 1: Illustration of the project idea and structure.

3. Project available results

The main results of the project constitute:

1. An ontology network for data documentation in the CE, called CEON¹[1], together with new knowledge on ontology engineering methodologies, and tool support (such as the use of LLMs for ontology engineering, c.f. [2, 3]).

¹<https://w3id.org/CEON>

2. The open circularity platform²[4], as a demonstration of how the Solid family of emerging standards can be applied to support CE data sharing needs.
3. An extension of the Circularity Thinking methodology³ and tools for innovation and analysis of CE value networks.
4. Mappings of example material and information flows in the three use case domains, as well as evaluations of the solutions in these three cases⁴.

4. Relevance to ESWC conference

The project applies core Semantic Web technologies to a new domain, and shows considerable benefits of the solutions for current industry challenges. As such, the project is a very good showcase for the application of the Semantic Web. Two of the main project results include (1) a core ontology network, which can be used and built on by others, as well as used for further alignment of other industry domains to the CE, and (2) a Solid-based platform for data sharing, which illustrates a new innovative use of Solid for confidential company data. Beyond the concrete exploitable artefacts and learnings from the applications, Onto-DESIDE has also fostered research on ontology engineering methodologies, e.g. LLM-supported ontology engineering as presented in the main research track both at ESWC 2024[2] and 2025 [3], as well as work presented in the KG4S workshop both in 2024[5, 4] and submitted to the 2025 edition.

5. Value brought by the project to ESWC participants

The project brings on one hand knowledge from the application of Semantic Web technologies in CE back to the Semantic Web research community, including new research problems that are triggered by needs in the CE setting. On the other hand, the concrete artefacts, such as the ontology network and the platform implementation, which are both open source, can be further used by other researchers and practitioners.

6. Value gained by the project from ESWC participation

As the project is coming to an end this year, we are on one hand looking for opportunities to further disseminate and spread the word about the concrete project results and exploitable artefacts. This could include early adopters in industry who would like to test our ontologies and the platform for their CE collaborations, or the methodology support for analysing their networks and find new innovation opportunities. On the other hand, the CE holds many unsolved challenges, including technical ones, beyond the scope of the project, and we hope to spur discussion on how the Semantic Web could potentially help to solve those in the future. The latter could also lead to discussions on further projects, and new collaborations within the Semantic Web community. One such collaboration opportunity comes in the form of a newly formed W3C community group⁵ on circular economy and Digital Product Passports, which the project initiated, and where we would like to gather more expertise and discussions around these topics.

²<https://github.com/KnowledgeOnWebScale/open-circularity-platform>

³Earlier version of the methods are described here in the context of the Climate KIC: <https://www.climate-kic.org/spotlight-initiatives/circularity-thinking-programme/>

⁴C.f. mappings described in D6.1-D6.3 and evaluation results in D6.7-D6.9 on the project results page: <https://ontodeside.eu/results/>

⁵<https://www.w3.org/community/ce-dpp/>

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